

NOVEL CARBON FIBER REINFORCED STAMPABLE POLYPROPYLENE SHEET WITH HIGH INTERFACIAL STRENGTH

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1 Introduction

Carbon-fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRP) are widely applied in aerospace, sports and other industrial fields. Recently, CFRP using thermoplastic matrices (CFRTP) are attracted due to high-cycle molding ability and recyclability.

Injection molding and compression molding are general methods of molding CFRTP. In these methods, discontinuous carbon fiber (CF) composites are frequently used to deal with complex-shaped components having curved surface and rib structures. However, discontinuous fiber-reinforced plastic is usually much weaker than continuous fiber-reinforced plastic. Moreover, biased fiber orientation often becomes a quality control problem. To overcome these issues, we developed fiber-length controlled, isotropic discontinuous CF mat, which is precursor of CFRTP stampable sheet (Fig. 1). By controlling CF length appropriately, this CFRTP stampable sheet is expected superior composite strength, almost equivalent to that of continuous fiber-reinforced plastics. In the case of polypropylene matrix, however, composite strength is insufficient due to low compatibility between CF and matrix resin.

In this work, improvement of interfacial strength between CF and polypropylene was studied to

Fig. 1. CFRTP stampable sheet

produce high-performance CFRTP stampable sheet with polypropylene matrix.

2. Improving interfacial strength

2.1 Evaluation of interfacial strength

There are some test methods of single fiber composite to evaluate interfacial strength between CF and matrix resin (Table 1). Of course, it is preferable to prepare the test piece easily and evaluate interfacial strength accurately. In consideration of evaluation difficulty and accuracy, we selected the fragmentation method to evaluate quantitative interfacial strength.

The test piece of the fragmentation method is a dumbbell-shaped resin in which single CF embedded (Fig. 2). Under the tensile test condition,

Table 1 Test methods of evaluating interfacial strength.

	fragmentation	pull-out	push-out	microdroplet
Model				
Evaluation difficulty	○	×	×	○
Evaluation accuracy	○	×	×	×

the CF breaks along with the increase of the test piece elongation. By counting the number of broken CF, interfacial shear strength can be calculated. We arranged the fragmentation method suitable for thermosetting matrices to obtain reliable interfacial strength data.

Determination of ideal interfacial strength (interfacial shear strength (IFSS)) between CF and polypropylene matrix is also important to set the target value of interfacial strength. We estimated the number of broken CF fragments by using analytical technique developed by Tohoku University [1], [2]. Fig. 2 shows calculated and experimental result of the ideal number of broken CF fragments for ideal adhesion between CF and polypropylene matrix. This result indicates that there is a strong possibility to improve the interfacial strength between CF and polypropylene.

2.2 Development of interfacial strength

To improve interfacial strength, we made original interfacial design for CFRTP stampable sheet. Especially, we developed specific interfacial layer for CF and polypropylene. The interfacial layer has good compatibility with both CF and polypropylene.

Fig. 1 Test piece of fragmentation method.

Fig. 2 Calculated and experimental results of fragmentation method (polypropylene matrix).

Fig. 3 Image of interfacial layer.

Fig. 4 Calculated and experimental results of fragmentation method (polypropylene matrix).

Fig. 3 shows the image of the interfacial layer. The interfacial layer contains polar groups having excellent compatibility with CF surface, and nonpolar groups having excellent compatibility with polypropylene. As a result of screening tests, we developed the new interfacial layer having almost ideal number of broken CF fragments as shown in Fig.4.

2.3 Mechanical properties of CFRTP stampable sheet

Fig. 5 presents the flexural properties of CFRTP stampable sheet. CFRTP (developed) exhibits higher strength than that of conventional one. And the strength of CFRTP (developed) is about twice that of GMT.

The fracture patterns for case of conventional type (a) and developed type (b) are depicted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5 Comparison of flexural properties. (VF of 20%, polypropylene)

Fig. 6 Comparison of fracture patterns. (a) CFRTP stampable sheet (conventional) (b) CFRTP stampable sheet (developed)

We observe that the CF surface is fully covered with polypropylene matrix in CFRTP stampable sheet (developed). On the other hand, the CF surface is not covered sufficiently in CFRTP stampable sheet (conventional). It is clear that the new interfacial layer is better for interfacial strength between CF and polypropylene.

3. Conclusion

We produced a novel high-performance CFRTP stampable sheet with polypropylene matrix using the following new development. The CFRTP stampable sheet is suitable for industrial use.

- (1) In fragmentation method of evaluating interfacial strength, the number of broken CF fragments for ideal adhesion between CF and polypropylene was estimated by using analytical technique developed by Tohoku University.
- (2) A new interfacial layer was developed to improve the adhesion between CF and polypropylene matrix.

4. Acknowledgements

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References

- [1] T. Okabe, M Takeda "Elastoplastic shear-lag analysis of single-fiber composites and strength prediction of unidirectional multi-fiber composites". *Composites Part A*, Vol. 33, pp 1327-1335, 2002.
- [2] T. Okabe, M Nishikawa, M Takeda, H Sekine "Effect of matrix hardening on the tensile strength of alumina fiber-reinforced aluminum matrix composites". *Acta Materialia*, Vol. 54, pp 2557-2566, 2006.